

Comparison of the Grid Forming and Grid Following Inverters Connected to a Real Grid

Jovana Glušćević¹[0009-0008-9418-4416], Žarko Janda¹[0000-0002-5696-0399],
Jasna Dragosavac¹[0000-0001-5935-2084]

¹ Electrical Engineering Institute Nikola Tesla, Koste Glavinića 8a, 11040 Belgrade, Serbia
jovana.gluscevic@ieent.org

Abstract. The growing utilization of wind and solar energy within energy grids has led to a demand for advanced technologies to oversee inverters effectively. These technologies are necessary for the smooth inclusion of renewable energy sources in the grid. Inverters hold a significant position in energy networks. For effective control of renewable energy sources, an understanding of the advantages and limitations of different types of inverters is necessary. This understanding can subsequently aid in constructing a power system characterized by reliability and ecological sustainability. The main goal of this paper is to explore the differences between grid-following (GFL) and grid-forming (GFM) inverters in power networks. It also provides insights into the advantages and disadvantages of GFL and GFM inverter controls and their impact on grid stability. The differences and features of each inverter are then compared using simulation results generated by the Matlab/Simulink software package. The control is realized using synchronverter's methods, varying the virtual moment of inertia and the damping factor for the purpose of achieving the desired response in case of network disturbances. The output variables are active and reactive power and they change according to control actions. Two scenarios are tested to compare the responses of GFM and GFL inverters: the grid disturbance and the change of reference value.

Keywords: Renewable energy sources, Grid-forming inverters, Grid-following inverters, Virtual moment of inertia, Virtual damping factor.

1 Introduction

Renewable sources of energy are currently one of the most relevant topics in terms of electricity production and environmental protection. Sources connected to the grid through inverters (Inverter-Based Resources, IBRs) are playing an increasingly significant role in the power system. Conventional synchronous generators (SG) support the grid by maintaining frequency within specified limits during disturbances, such as network faults or load changes, due to their inertia. In contrast to SGs, the dynamics of IBRs depend on control algorithms, enhancing their flexibility but potentially impacting the stability of the connected grid [1].

The issue of grid stability is becoming increasingly pronounced due to the growing replacement of conventional SGs with IBRs. One approach to overcoming this challenge is the development of optimal inverter control strategies, which is the focus of experts in this field. Inverters connected to the grid can be categorized as grid-following inverters (GFLI) and grid-forming inverters (GFMI). These two types of inverters are compared in numerous studies, such as [1] and [2]. The key difference lies in the parameters they control when linked to the grid. They also contrast in how they react to grid events, handle different network impedance conditions during connection, and synchronize with the grid. GFL requires a synchronization unit in its control algorithm, typically implemented using a phase-locked loop (PLL), which provides information about the grid voltage angle. Analysis in [3] demonstrates the adverse impact of PLL on inverter stability, particularly in networks with high network impedance.

The concept of GFM was introduced to improve grid stability as renewable energy sources like IBRs become more prevalent in the network. Fundamental control methods of GFM inverters and their characteristics are outlined in [4]. One such method is the "synchronverter," which forms the basis of this study. The control algorithm of the synchronverter is derived from synchronous generator equations. When interconnected with the grid, the dynamics of the synchronverter, as seen from the grid, are equivalent to those of a synchronous generator [5]. However, this control implementation lacks a current loop, resulting in the occurrence of synchronous resonance [6]. The control algorithm utilized in this study has been enhanced by incorporating an internal current loop. In the work, the concept of the synchronous inverter was also used for the realization of the GFL

The paper is further organized into four sections. The second section explains grid-connected inverters and introduces key features of GFL and GFM inverters. The concept of the synchronverter and its improved control is presented in the third section. The fourth section examines results for GFL and GFM inverters in the same scenarios. Lastly, the fifth section summarizes the study's conclusions.

2 Basic concept of grid-connected inverters

The connection of renewable energy sources to the power grid, including solar and wind farms, is carried out through inverters. Depending on control implementation, grid interactions, and responses to grid changes, inverters can be divided into GFL and GFM inverters [4]. Simplified control schemes for GFM and GFL inverters are presented in Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Control scheme) GFL inverter, b) GFM inverter.

2.1 Grid-following inverters

Power regulation in GFL inverters is achieved by injecting a specific current into the grid, allowing such an inverter to be approximated as a current-controlled source with impedance in parallel, as shown in Fig. 1a [4]. The synchronization unit is an indispensable component of GFL inverters and is depicted in Fig. 1a. Its goal is to gather data about the grid voltage angle, which is then utilized to compute the necessary phase shift in currents for injecting the intended active and reactive power into the grid. The PLL is often used for synchronization, but it can negatively affect inverter stability [3].

2.2 Grid-forming inverters

GFM inverters directly control the voltage and frequency at their output terminals. They can be approximated as voltage-controlled sources with series impedance, as shown in Fig. 1b [4]. Unlike GFL inverters that follow the angle of the grid voltage, GFM inverters control the frequency. As such, they are not only employed in microgrids but are also utilized to enhance stability in networks with a significant share of IBRs [2].

3 Synchronverter

The research utilized a control strategy derived from the mathematical model of a synchronous generator. Inverters imitating synchronous generator behavior are termed "synchronverters" [5]. Unlike conventional synchronous generators with fixed inertia and damping values, synchronverters enable parameter adjustments.

In contrast to [7], the control approach was improved by integrating an internal current loop. Although initially intended for GFM inverter, the control concept of the synchronverter has been adjusted, incorporating specific modifications, to suit the implementation of a GFL inverter.

3.1 Improved synchronverter control method

Fig. 1 displays the block diagram of the enhanced synchronverter. The differences in forming GFL and GFM inverters are illustrated in red and blue, respectively. For GFL formation, the first derivative of the grid voltage angle, obtained from the PLL, is substituted in place of the nominal angular frequency. Additionally, the voltage drop loop is neglected in the case of GFL. The constant Dp represents the sum of the damping coefficient and frequency droop coefficient [5]. The parameter J signifies the virtual moment of inertia. The study evaluated the impact of these parameters on inverter stability, making a comparison between GFM and GFL implementations. The response was compared under changes in active power reference and disturbances in the grid for various values of parameters Dp , J , and Lm , where Lm denotes grid inductance. Moreover, the influence of the integral action of the PI controller in the PLL on inverter stability was examined.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of improved synchronverter control method.

4 Validation of synchronverter results with enhanced control algorithm

The simulation was conducted using the Matlab/Simulink software package. The inverter was connected to the distribution network (400 V, 50Hz) through an LCL filter, and the network was modeled using a Thevenin generator. An X/R ratio of 1 was adopted [8]. The process of inverter connection to the grid was not considered in this study. The following changes were simulated: at time $t_1 = 2$ s, a reference active power of 5 kW was set for an inverter that was previously unloaded. A disturbance in the form of a sudden 1% decrease in the grid voltage frequency was introduced at $t_2 = 2.5$ s.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 depict the responses to changes in active power for GFM and GFL inverters, respectively, for different values of parameters Dp , and Lm . It can be observed that increasing the damping coefficient Dp results in a slower and more damped response in both cases. The impact of changing grid inductance Lm varies. As grid inductance rises, the stability of the GFL inverter decreases due to insufficient response damping (Fig. 4). Conversely, the GFM inverter exhibits a more stable response with higher network inductance values (Fig. 3). For better understanding and analysis, Fig. 5 presents the pole-zero plot of the transfer function for both the GFM inverter (marked as "x") and the GFL inverter (marked as "*"). Within Fig. 5, three groups of poles are displayed for each scenario shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. These groups demonstrate how the poles shift as the virtual inertia J changes. The arrows indicate the direction of pole movement with increasing virtual inertia J , revealing that higher inertia leads to more oscillatory responses. The effect of raising the damping factor Dp is more pronounced in the case of the GFM inverter (blue "x" in Fig. 5), where a sufficient increase in Dp can lead to a response without overshooting (Fig. 3). As observed in both time-domain graphs and Fig. 5, increasing grid inductance Lm brings the poles of the GFL inverter closer to the imaginary axis (red "*" in Fig. 5). Consequently, GFM not only displays improved damping attributes with Dp values but also showcases better performance in networks with higher impedance.

In Fig. 6, the integral action ki of the PI controller within the PLL was reduced. The poles of the GFM inverter are shown under the same conditions as in Fig. 5, with their positions unchanged. The position of the GFL inverter poles changed with variations in the integral action ki . The most significant change occurred during changes in grid impedance (red "*"). It can be observed that for a smaller value of the parameter ki , the poles are farther away from the imaginary axis, resulting in a more damped and slower response. This highlights the importance of carefully tuning the PLL controller in GFL, as its action significantly affects inverter stability.

Fig. 3. Response to a step change in the reference of active power of a GFMI

Fig. 4 Response to a step change in the reference of active power of a GFLI

Fig. 5. Pole positions of the transfer function GFMI (x) i GFLI ($*$) for $k_i = 10$

Fig. 6. Pole positions of the transfer function GFMI (x) i GFLI ($*$) for $k_i = 1$

Fig. 7 illustrates the response to a disturbance in the form of a change in grid frequency. The change in frequency within the grid has a varying impact on the two types of inverters analyzed. GFM inverters, approximated as voltage sources, primarily aim to regulate the voltage and frequency of the grid. As a result, active and reactive powers change to achieve this goal (Fig. 7a). On the other hand, for GFL inverters approximated as current sources, the main objective is to regulate the power injected into the grid, with grid support being a secondary goal (Fig. 7b).

Fig. 7. Block diagram of improved synchronverter control method.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the study investigated the control and stability aspects of GFM and GFL inverters using an enhanced synchronverter concept. The control scheme was analyzed through simulations, focusing on parameters such as Dp , J , and Lm . The impact of these parameters on inverter stability and performance was evaluated. Notably, increasing Dp led to slower and more damped responses in both GFM and GFL inverters. Grid inductance Lm affects stability differently: GFL inverters became less stable due to insufficiently damped response, while GFM inverters exhibited improved stability with higher Lm values. The pole-zero plots illustrated how the virtual inertia J influenced oscillatory behavior, while adjusting the integral action ki in the PLL revealed its crucial role in GFL inverter stability. Moreover, the response of GFM and GFL inverters to grid frequency changes was highlighted, emphasizing their distinct roles in regulating voltage and power injection. Finally, this study endeavoured to enhance our comprehension of inverter operations, ultimately hoping to pave the way for actualization of reliable and efficient strategies in integrating renewable energy into power grids.

6 Acknowledgment

This work was supported in part by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia under the Contract on the realization and financing of the scientific research work of Research and Innovation Organizations in 2023.

References

1. Li, Y., Gu, Y., Green, T. C.: Revisiting grid-forming and grid-following inverters: A duality theory. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 37 (6), 4541–4554 (2022).

2. Pattabiraman, D., Lasseter, R. H., Jahns, T. M.: Comparison of grid following and grid forming control for a high inverter penetration power system. 2018 IEEE Power & Energy Society General Meeting (PESGM), Portland, OR, USA, pp. 1–5. (2018).
3. Wen, B., Boroyevich, D., Burgos, R., Mattavelli, P., Shen, Z.: Analysis of D-Q small-signal impedance of grid-tied inverters. *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics* 31(1), 675–687 (2016).
4. Rathnayake, D. B. et al.: Grid forming inverter modeling, control, and applications. *IEEE Access* 9, 114781–114807 (2021).
5. Zhong, Q.-C., Weiss, G.: Synchronverters: Inverters that mimic synchronous generators. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 58(4), 1259–1267 (2011).
6. Roldán-Pérez, J., González-Cajigas, A., Rodríguez-Cabero, A., Prodanovic, M., Zumel, P.: Design and analysis of a current-controlled virtual synchronous machine for weak grids. 2019 IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC), Anaheim, CA, USA, pp. 1459–1465, (2019).
7. Zhong, Q.-C., Nguyen, P.-L., Ma, Z., Sheng, W.: Self-synchronized synchronverters: Inverters without a dedicated synchronization unit. *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics* 29(2), 617–630 (2014).
8. Birchfield, A.B.; Schweitzer, E.; Athari, M.H.; Xu, T.; Overbye, T.J.; Scaglione, A.; Wang, Z.: A metric-based validation process to assess the realism of synthetic power grids. *Energies* 10, 1233 (2017).